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Knowledge, Skill and Attitude (KSA) as determinants of Overall Team Performance of a Chorale Group in a Local City College in Angeles City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This present study aims to determine the relationship between Knowledge, Skill, Attitude and Team Performance of a Chorale Group. The respondents of this study are the members of Tinig Angeleño at A Local City College. There are two questionnaires that were used: The Team Performance Scale and The KSA Questionnaire. The KSAQ was formulated for the study and underwent pilot testing to non-Chorale Group students (N=73) with ($\alpha = .885, .810$ and $.896$) which confirms that the instrument can be used for the study; while TPS was used to describe the overall team performance of the group. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to describe KSA and Team Performance while Spearman's rho was used to determine the relationship between KSA and Team Performance. After data were gathered from 15 members of the Chorale Group it was found out that the KSA and team performance of the chorale members is high. In regards to the relationship between KSA and Team Performance, it was found out that there is a significant relationship between Attitude and Team Performance, while there was no significant relationship observed to the knowledge and skill of members to their team performance. From the obtained results, it is highly recommended to conduct studies regarding the relationship of knowledge, skills, and attitude with team performance to a larger population, not only in a vicinity of the college. These results provide new information to the students and experts who have an interest in conducting the same study. Further investigation in this research study is highly recommended.

INTRODUCTION

In early 2020, China saw an outbreak of a novel, sometimes fatal, severe respiratory sickness. The virus was initially detected in Hubei Province in December 2019, when a cluster of viral pneumonia cases was reported. The cause of pneumonia has been identified as a new coronavirus. The virus, then known as 2019-nCoV (now known as SARS-CoV-2), caused a massive pandemic across the country. The Covid-19 pandemic forced choirs to stop doing things in person, providing a unique opportunity to not only investigate the social value of virtual choir experiences but also to consider the wider impact on choir participants and their perceptions of their "choir" once defining elements of the activity are no longer active (Daffern, et. al., 2021). Recent research of Scandinavian choirs forced to halt operations during a partial societal lockdown in the spring of 2020 emphasizes the social aspects of the activity even more. In the academe setting here in the Philippines, most of the choir groups operations such as training and performance were stopped due to the rapid spread of the virus in the country.

Chorale

Chorale group or sometimes called as is a musical ensemble, also known as "choir" or "musical group". A group of persons who play instrumental or vocal music, usually under the ensemble's name. Some music groups, such as a jazz quartet or an orchestra, are made up entirely of instruments. It allows developing the skills, knowledge and attitude of a member. Students learn to listen and non-verbally communicate with one another to

produce music as a group, whether they have the melody or harmony (Kansas Curricular Standards for Music Education, 1998a). A group Performance is a group of people who performs in an orchestra.

Based on our understanding of modern-day primitive peoples' singing, a conceivable musical growth scenario would begin with rudimentary melodic patterns based on several tones. Following that, pitch matching several people singing in unison, singing in parallel motion as a natural byproduct of women or children singing with men, call-and-response phrases, drone basses, and canon as the following stages. All of this might lead to the creation of fundamental musical techniques like melodic sequences and cadential formulas and an emerging understanding of tonic and scale structure (early music frequently employs pentatonic scales).

Knowledge, Skills and Attitude (KSA)

Knowledge is defined as the structure and context of a music. The structure is the knowledge which describes how the elements of music such as pitch, rhythm, harmony, dynamics, timbre, texture, form, and style are used within a piece and the difficulty or challenges of music being performed or created.

Skills are how you can create and the ability to do something well. Performance abilities and attributes that are required at a given grade or level are referred to as this category of capabilities. Technique, sound quality, technical precision, interpretation and expression, and ensemble abilities are among them, as are effective techniques to selecting and programming acceptable works for performance and improving work employing

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effective practice strategies and work habits. It also includes the presenting or performance of work that demonstrates proper manners and demeanor. Singing, playing instruments, and movement are all ways to express these abilities.

Attitude is the qualities of the character and mind. Here comes flexibility, goal-setting, and responsibility for risk-taking, self-discipline, and Perseverance. The ability to see and hear different points of view and monitor and/or alter work based on input from various sources and under varying situations setting definite and time-bound deadlines for work completion. Willing to take risks when facing difficult musical or ensemble problems with no obvious or traditional solutions and to view these challenges as opportunities for learning and progress. While aiming for excellence, demonstrating independence and self-motivation, regulating impulsivity, and learning or applying delayed gratification are all important (Kansas Curricular Standards for Music Education, 1998a). Attitude has a huge impact on people. It influences how they perceive individuals, how they feel about them, and how they sound. Having a positive mindset permits people to walk onstage without being distracted by negative thoughts.

Knowledge, Skills and Attitude vis-à-vis Team Performance

A study was conducted to show the attitude of high school students in terms of their chorale experience and the relationship of performance. The researchers surveyed some respondents, such as students and conductors, about the value they put in conducting behavior in chorale rehearsal. The students value more about personality and personal qualities of the conductors than conducting and rehearsal procedures (Gleason, 1992). In the Study of Kirrane, et. al. (2016) The choir's group procedures were compared to typical models of effective teamwork in the analysis. The findings imply that some aspects of this choir's dynamics go beyond traditional notions of teamwork. More conceptual and empirical study is needed to build a model of cooperation that can be applied to the conditions of performance-based teams and inform choral practice and training. Every organization's group performance is critical since it represents its overall performance. If different people in a company cannot work together, the company's financial and operational performance can never be optimal. Every successful organization relies heavily on group efforts and teamwork, which necessitates ensuring that each group member's personality is compatible with the groups/goals. Organizations there can never be a good group without decent individuals within it.

Study of Koster and Aven (2018) stated that individuals' status may benefit or suffer due to their identification with their groups, depending on their performance. When the group performs well, high-status members may receive a large portion of the credit and gain status. High-status members of underperforming groups, on the other hand, may experience disproportionate status decreases when

compared to low-status group members. As a result, we expect a relationship between group performance and overall status in terms of group and member readiness to associate. As Stated by Dingle, et. al. (2016), Choral singers also thought their choirs were a more cohesive or 'meaningful' social group than team sport players thought their teams were. These data could be construed to show that choral singers' psychological well-being is influenced more by their membership in a group than by their singing.

Study findings of Sabri & Abu-Atiah (2020) revealed that teamwork KSA has a significant relationship with Team performance. In the study of Latif & Williams (2016), the result findings revealed the determinants of effective team performance of NGOs are knowledge, skills and attitude, and along side other constructs. On the other hand, study findings of Siassakos et al. (2010) revealed that there is no significant relationship between knowledge, skill and attitude to team performance. Based on the literature review and analysis performed, the researchers have come up with the hypothesis:

H0: There is a statistically significant relationship between knowledge, skill and attitude (KSA) to team performance. All literatures that were mentioned will be used as basis for this foregoing search for answer. In line with this, it aims to determine the relationship between Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes (KSA) to Team Performance of the Chorale Group of City College of Angeles. It aims to answer the following research questions:

- 1.How may the respondents' knowledge, skill, and attitude (KSA) be described?
- 2.How may the level of the team performance of the chorale group be described?
- 3.Is there a significant relationship between knowledge, skill and attitude to team performance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design, Population and Sampling, Instrument, Procedure and Analysis Design, Population and Sampling

This present study is quantitative-correlational which aims to determine the relationship between the Knowledge, Skills and Attitude (KSA) to the Team performance of CCA Tinig Angeleño. The sampling technique that was used is Purposive Sampling. The target respondents of this study are the members of the said chorale group. Raosoft Sample Size Calculator was used to determine the target sample size of respondents from the total population. The total population of members of the chorale group is fifteen (15) and the target sample size is fifteen (15) with 5% margin of error and 95% level of confidence.

Instrument

There are two questionnaires that were used for this study. In which, the first questionnaires that was utilized for this study has been formulated and created by the researchers. The instrument aims to describe respondents' Knowledge, Skill and Attitude in singing. It was named as

“Knowledge, Skill and Attitude Questionnaire (KSAQ)”. It is a 15-item questionnaire subdivided into three (3) categories: Knowledge (K), Skill (S) and Attitude (A). Responses are then recorded by a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). The formulated questionnaire undergone Pilot testing for BPA students (N=73), where Cronbach’s Alpha for Knowledge is ($\alpha = .882$), in Skills is ($\alpha = .810$) and in Attitude is ($\alpha = .894$). Internal consistencies of all categories are Good (>0.8), (>0.8) and (>0.8). Therefore, the tool can be used for the conduct of study.

Second, the Team Performance Scale (TPS) is a 18-item questionnaire adapted from Thompson et al. (2009) which measures the quality of team’s interaction and performances. Responses are then recorded on a 4-point Likert scale from 1 ‘none of the time’ to 4 ‘all the time.’ In the original study of Thompson et. al., the scale’s Cronbach’s Alpha Value is 0.97 which can be used for the conduct of this study.

Pilot Testing Phase

In order to gather data from the participants, a letter was addressed and sent to the Dean of the Institute of Education, Arts and Sciences (IEAS) of City College of Angeles obtaining approval for the conduct of the pilot study. When the approval was obtained, the survey was forwarded via Google form link which can be answered for 10-15 minutes. All gathered data from the Google were exported to an excel file in analyzation of the KSAQ’s reliability.

Conduct of Study Phase

After confirming the questionnaire’s reliability analysis, another letter was sent through electronic mail to the Dean for the flotation of the two survey questionnaires. When the approval has been obtained, the survey

questionnaires were forwarded to all participants via Google from link. All gathered data were exported to an excel file for analysis.

The statistical treatment that were used to describe the knowledge, skill, attitude and level of group performance of the respondents are Frequency (f), Percentage (%), Mean (M) and Standard deviation (SD). Lastly, to determine the relationship between the variables knowledge, skill and attitude (KSA) to team performance (TP), Spearman-rho was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the respondents’ knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards chorale group performance using KSAQ. While knowledge got the highest overall mean of 3.80 among the three variables, it also got the lowest overall standard deviation of 0.26. Meanwhile, the overall mean and standard deviation for respondents’ skill are 2.92 and 0.49, respectively. Results also reveal that the overall attitude got a mean of 3.52, and a standard deviation of 0.4. Statements from all the variables impacted the results as shown in the table. For knowledge, respondents strongly agree that vocalization every morning conditions their voice (M=3.81, SD=0.54), and breathing exercises help them to properly control their voices (M=3.94, SD=0.25). For skills, though respondents strongly disagree that they can make whistle notes (M=1.50, SD=0.92), a firm agreement from them favor covering songs in their own version (M=3.44, SD=0.63) and performing songs in different genres (M=3.38, SD=0.72). And for attitude, CCA Tinig Angelenos strongly agree that they always keep their attention on their co-performer to harmonize their voices and actions (M=3.75, SD=0.45) and that they do humming for some vocal exercises (M=3.81, SD=0.40).

Table 1: Level of Knowledge, Skills and Attitude (KSA) of Chorale Members

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Knowledge			
1. Vocalization every morning helps condition my voice.	3.81	0.54	Strongly Agree
2. Breathing exercises help me to properly control my voice.	3.94	0.25	Strongly Agree
3. Drinking warm water before and after performance keeps my larynx in good condition	3.63	0.62	Strongly Agree
4. Ginger tea prevents itchiness of the larynx making voice out smoothly.	3.69	0.48	Strongly Agree
5. Observing your emotions while performing	3.94	0.25	Strongly Agree
Total	3.80	0.26	Strongly Agree
Skills			
1. Do cover song in my own version etc.	3.44	0.63	Strongly Agree
2. Perform songs in different genre.	3.38	0.72	Strongly Agree
3. I can do whistle note.	1.50	0.82	Strongly Disagree
4. I can do both lower and higher notes	3.06	0.77	Strongly Agree
5. I can easily memorize lyrics before performance.	3.25	0.68	Strongly Agree
Total	2.92	0.48	Agree
Attitude			
1. I practice my singing tone regularly.	3.50	0.63	Strongly Agree
2. I always keep my Attention with co performers for the harmonization of voices and actions.	3.75	0.45	Strongly Agree
3. I do humming for some vocal exercises.	3.81	0.40	Strongly Agree
4. Every rehearsal I am never late.	3.25	0.77	Strongly Agree
5. During my free time, I frequently watch voice tutorials.	3.31	0.70	Strongly Agree
Total	3.52	0.40	Strongly Agree

Table 2. Level of Team Performance of the Chorale Group

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. All team members made an effort to participate in discussions.	3.56	0.63	All of the times
2. When team members had different opinions, each member explained his/her point of view.	3.56	0.51	All of the times
3. Team members encouraged one another to express their opinions and thoughts.	3.56	0.51	All of the times
4. Team members shared and received criticism without making it personal.	3.50	0.52	All of the times
5. Different points of view were respected by team members.	3.44	0.63	All of the times
6. Often members helped a fellow team member to be understood by paraphrasing what he/she was saying.	3.75	0.45	All of the times
7. My team used several techniques for problem solving (such as brainstorming) with each team member presenting his/her best ideas.	3.63	0.50	All of the times
8. Team members worked to come up with solutions that satisfied all members.	3.63	0.50	All of the times
9. All team members consistently paid attention during group discussions.	3.50	0.52	All of the times
10. My team actively elicited multiple points of view before deciding on a final answer.	3.56	0.51	All of the times
11. My team actively elicited multiple points of view before deciding on a final answer.	3.63	0.50	All of the times
12. Team members listened to each other when someone expressed a concern about individual or team performance.	3.50	0.52	All of the times
13. Team members willingly participated in all relevant aspects of the team.	3.44	0.51	All of the times
14. Team members resolved differences of opinion by openly speaking their mind.	3.56	0.51	All of the times
15. Team members used feedback about individual or team performance to help the team be more effective.	3.50	0.52	All of the times
16. Team members seemed were saying when they spoke.	3.56	0.51	All of the times
17. My team resolved many conflicts by compromising between team members, with each one giving in a little.	3.69	0.48	All of the times
18. Members who had different opinions explained their point of view to the team.	3.56	0.63	All of the times
Total	3.56	0.41	All of the times

Table 2 shows the team performance of the respondents using TPS. The overall mean and standard deviation for CCA Tinig Angelenos is 3.56 and 0.41, respectively. The overall results from this table are supported by the results gained from the statements. Respondents say that their co-members make an effort to participate in discussions (M=3.56, SD=0.63), When their team members have different opinions, each member explains their point-of-view of all of the time (M=3.56, SD=0.51). These opinions are also respected (M=3.44, SD=0.63), and that their team members always work to come up with solutions that will satisfy the rest (M=3.63, SD=0.50). Respondents also say that they value the feedback of each of the team at all times that can help improve their future

Table 3. Correlation between Knowledge, Skills and Attitude (KSA) and Team Performance

Group Performance	Team Performance	
	r	P
Knowledge	0.310	0.242
Skills	0.208	0.440
Attitude	0.801	<.001

performances (M=3.56, SD=0.51).

Table 3 illustrates the correlation between group and team performances' knowledge, skills, and attitude. Spearman's rho was used to determine the correlation between KSA and Team performance. knowledge, it was found out that there is no significant correlation between Knowledge and Team performance (p = 0.242). In Skill, there is no significant correlation between Skill and Team

performance (p = 0.440). On the other hand, the results show a significant correlation between Attitude and Team performance (p = <.001).

DISCUSSION

Knowledge

After the analysis of data, the result findings revealed that most of the members of the CCA Tinig Angeleno in terms of their Knowledge (K) are highly educated on what they should do in order for them to be on shape in terms of singing. Most of the dancers perform vocalization every morning in order condition their body and voice before performance. Warmups prepare singers for the intense vibration that comes along with singing. Controlled, steady vocal exercises increase acid in the muscles surrounding your vocal folds, which helps the muscles do their jobs more effectively. According to Gish et al. (2012), vocal warm-up exercises contributes to the prevention of vocal fold injury for professional voice users. Both professional singers and students of singing consider a regular vocal warm-up regimen essential. It was also found out that most of the members of the chorale are performing breathing exercise so that they can properly control their voice. This can be supported by the study findings of Gul (2018) where it revealed that music teachers/conductors employs breathing exercises because it has a positive effect on the voice control of the students. Also, chorale members have been found out that they drink warm water before and after performance to keep their larynx in good condition. Drinking water

is most obvious cure for vocal fold/tissue hydration (Nichols, 2010). Chorale members are also educated that ginger tea prevents itchininess of the larynx making voice out smoothly. Calcinoni et al. (2021) stated that, tea and ginger are some of the widely diffused and commonly use for specific activities on voice. Lastly, chorale members are educated that observation of emotions during performing is important. It can be stated that most of the members are knowledgeable when to apply the correct emotions into performance. Singing is not only about voice performance, but emotions as well add spice in the overall performance. Singers use facial expression and head movements in ways that correlates with the intended emotion (Quinto et al., 2014).

Skills

Based from the results, findings yielded that chorale members of the organization do cover song on their own version, perform songs in different genre, can do both lower and higher notes and can easily memorize lyrics before performance. On the other side, members are not capable of executing whistle notes. According to previously conducted researches, anyone can sing in whistle register. However, in order for singers to hit a whistle note, it will require some special vocal exercises to successfully execute.

Attitudes

Results stated that chorale members are highly positive based on their attitudes toward singing and their individual performance. Firstly, most of the members practice their singing tone regularly. Focused attention on intonation can improve the ear for music and develop enjoyable, comfortable singing. Secondly, members always keep their attention with their co-members in harmonizing their voices and actions. This can be stated that members are highly attentive with what notes they are singing in order to harmonize with their co-members in the chorale. Also, it was found out that members perform humming for some vocal exercises. According the researches, humming is actually one of the best vocal warm-ups because it doesn't put a lot of strain on your vocal cords. It also clears someone's tone and make vocal muscles more flexible. If one always execute humming as part of their vocal exercise, overtime, it will increase the bass and depth of voice and increases control on the voice too. Additionally, most of the members have never been late during their rehearsals. This is a good indication of a responsible member and appreciates the precious time of others, and it decreases any possibilities of delays or extension of time during practice or rehearsals. Lastly, it was also found out that during the free time of members, they frequently watch voice tutorials. Video tutorials can be viewed on computers through websites, and online streams, as well as with other mobile devices, such as smartphones. This provide accessibility to the chorale members to extend their learning more in singing.

Overall, it can be stated that most of the members are well-versed based on their KSA. This is supported by Stevens & Campion's (1994) stating the importance of

knowledge, skills, and attitude in teamwork. They said that the three are needed to be addressed as they play a vital role in team-oriented environments of today's world.

Level of Team Performance

The level of the team performance of the CCA Tinig Angeleño was found out to be very high. Meaning, most of the members are highly engaged and participative, on both before and after performance of the organization. This can be stated that the team is working well with group performance (Thompson, et. al., 2009). Also, that when a group works together hand-in-hand, a better outcome is yet to be achieved (Schmutz, et. al., 2014). Research shows that collaborative problem solving leads to better outcomes. Overall, everyone must not be complacent so a harmonious relationship will be built among the team members .

Relationship between Knowledge, Skill and Attitude to Level of Team Performance

Based on the findings from the Spearman-rho analysis, it was found out there a significant relationship between Attitude and TP which accepted the hypothesis for the study; and, rejected the hypothesis which correlates Knowledge (K) and Skill (S) to TP. This claim may be supported by the findings of Ogilo et al. (2020), where it was found out that the employee's attitude was found out to have a positive significant effect on organizational performances. On other hand, This was contradicted by the result finding of Mousavi et al. (2018), wherein the result revealed that positive attitude has no significant relationship toward the effectiveness of teamwork. On the other hand, there was no significant relationship observed between Knowledge (K) and Skill (S) to TP. Previous conducted studies have confirmed that Knowledge (S) and Skill (S) are related to TP. In this, it is highly recommended to conduct another study to other set of chorale group in order to determine if the claim of this study may be supported.

This study has several limitations. First, this study only focused on the chorale members of CCA Tinig Angeleño of the City College of Angeles. Meaning, the result of this study may not be applicable to other groups. In this, future researchers may be curious on conducting the same study from other higher education institutions (HEIs) or expansion of other respondents from the primary or secondary education sector, and compare if the results may be similar to support the claim of this present study. Also, future researchers may also add other variables such as moderating and mediating variables to further understand the relationship between KSA and Team Performance. Additionally, application of other research techniques such as qualitative or mixed method can be employed to this study to have a deeper understanding of the constructs that were measured in this study. Lastly, the result of this study contributes to the existing literatures regarding the relationship of KSA to TP.

CONCLUSIONS

This study sought to determine the relationship

between knowledge, skill and attitude (KSA) and the Team Performance (TP) of CCA Tinig Angeleños. The researchers understand the role of these three variables in group performance that is why, they followed a procedure to come up with conclusions for this study based on the obtained results. Using a series of survey which involved 15 respondents from the target population, the following are the conclusions drawn from the study: from the results of the survey using KSAQ, the findings revealed that the members of the chorale are knowledgeable, there is high level of seriousness on what they are doing, and they are all highly skillful. Overall, knowledge and attitude have a higher response rating from the population than the skill. This, however, does not mean that skill is less important than the two because it can be described that the three variables are still important when it comes to the overall group performance. In the findings using TPS, it was found out that team performance of the chorale group is high. It can be stated that the entire chorale group is doing well when it comes to their performance as a team. A positive significant relationship was observed between attitude and overall team performance of the chorale group. However, knowledge and skill were found out to be not statistically correlated with team performance. It can be concluded that, attitude can be claimed as one of the determinants in the overall team performance of the CCA Tinig Angeleño.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. Head of the Chorale group (Conductor) should assess students who are interested in being a member of the chorale. The Conductor should assess the students' attitude, especially how responsible they are as a singer, how they practice their singing tone regularly, what their daily routine is in terms of rehearsal, and how they perform with other performers (harmonization of voice action). In this way, the conductor will get enough idea if the students are qualified to join the Chorale.

2. Teachers and other Professionals in Schools who are experts in music should guide the students. They must provide seminars/webinars, training, and more exposure to the students to improve more, such as teaching appropriate routines to practice and improve the voice and proper rehearsal.

3. Observe the students on how they behave well, if they are attending practice regularly and if they are attending on time. Teachers, Conductors or Coaches should always tell the students to be on time because it is also one of their responsibilities. Being a responsible chorale member is one of the attitudes that they must possess.

4. Lastly, the researchers recommend conducting a more thorough study regarding the relationship of Knowledge, Skill and Attitude (KSA) to Team performance in a larger population, not only in a vicinity of a local city college. Further investigation is highly recommended for this study.

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